

Rearing pink stem borer *Sesamia inferens* on the southwestern corn borer diet

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For 2 yr, we have successfully reared dark-headed stem borer *Chilo polychrysus*, armyworm *Mythimna separata*, cutworm *Spodoptera mauritia*, and pink stem borer on the southwestern corn borer diet. We studied the effect of that diet and a rice stem diet on the growth and development of the pink stem borer.

Rearing on rice stems. Seedlings of susceptible Rexoro were transplanted in 30-cm-diam clay pots. Fifty days after transplanting tillers were cut at the base. Stems were cut into 10-cm pieces and placed in 50 vials, each 11 cm long. To prevent the stem pieces from drying, a film of water was maintained at the base of each vial.

Pink stem borer moths emerging from field-collected pupae were allowed to oviposit on Rexoro plants inside cages. Egg masses were kept in a rearing room maintained at 28-30 °C and 70-80% relative humidity (RH), and allowed to hatch. Each stem piece in the vial was infested with two newly hatched pink borer larvae. Twice weekly the stem pieces were replaced with fresh ones. Individual weights of last-instar larvae and pupae were recorded. Emerging adults were allowed to oviposit on Rexoro plants and the incubation period of eggs was recorded.

Rearing on the southwestern corn borer diet. Field-collected pupae were caged and emerging moths were allowed to oviposit on Rexoro plants. Egg masses were incubated at 28-30 °C and 70-80% RH.

One litre of the custom southwestern corn borer diet (Bio-Mix #9763) was prepared using the following ingredients and steps:

<i>Pack A</i>	g/litre
Agar	17.2
<i>Pack B - dry mix</i>	
Wheat germ, toasted	21.1
Sucrose	25.0
Casein, vitamin-free	25.0
Salt mix Wesson	7.0
Linseed oil	0.2

Table 1. Duration of egg, larval, and pupal stages and length of life of adult pink stem borer reared on rice stems or southwestern corn borer diet.

Insect stage	Duration (d)			
	Rice stem		Artificial diet	
	Av	Range	Av	Range
Egg	7.6 ± 1.0	6-9	6.5 ± 1.1	5-8
Larva	28.9 ± 3.8	22-35	22.1 ± 5.9	18-33
Pupa	8.4 ± 1.1	7-10	10.6 ± 1.1	9-13
Adult	4.9 ± 0.9	3-6	3.3 ± 0.5	3-4

Table 2. Weights of last-instar larvae and pupae of pink stem borer when reared on rice stems or the southwestern corn borer diet.

Insect stage	Weight (mg)			
	Rice stem		Artificial diet	
	Av	Range	Av	Range
Larva	170.0 ± 46.5	112.1 - 279.6	217.3 ± 46.9	133.0 - 296.0
Pupa				
Female	164.7 ± 22.2	130.3 - 206.5	209.9 ± 38.8	163.6 - 278.0
Male	123.1 ± 20.6	92.0 - 183.9	148.2 ± 48.2	118.6 - 168.6

- Cholesterol 0.1
- Corn cob grits (autoclaved) 37.0
- Methylparaben 1.5
- Sorbic acid 0.5
- Pack C - vitamins*
- Vanderzant vitamin mix 5.3
- Ascorbic acid 2.1

1. Bring 545 ml of distilled water to a rolling boil.
2. Add 17.2 g of agar and stir until most of the agar has dissolved.
3. Pour water-agar mixture into the blender.
4. Add 118 g of pack B to the mixture and mix for 3 min at high speed.
5. Pour 366 ml of chilled distilled water into the blender and mix for 1 min.
6. Add 7.4 g of vitamins (pack C) and mix for 1 min.
7. Pour into rearing cups. If bacterial contamination is a problem, add with the vitamins 4 ml of 10% formaldehyde or 125 mg of aureomycin or both.

When the mixture cooled and the sides of the cup were dry, each cup was infested with two newly hatched pink stem borer larvae. Fifty cups were maintained for observation. Insect survival and growth duration of larvae and pupae were noted for each cup and individual weights were taken of last-instar larvae and pupae. The resulting moths were allowed to oviposit

on rice plants and incubation periods of the eggs taken.

Larval development was more rapid on the southwestern corn borer diet. The larval stage took 22 d versus 29 d for the rice stem diet (Table 1). The length of the egg and pupal stages were similar on the two food sources. Weights of last-instar larvae and pupae were distinctly higher on the southwestern corn borer diet, indicating that it is a better food source than rice stems (Table 2). □

Yellow stem borer (YSB) survival as affected by growth stage of early and medium-duration rices

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Previous studies have shown that IR46 is more resistant to the YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* at panicle initiation than at other growth stages. To determine the effect of growth stage on YSB survival from larva to adult, medium-duration IR46 was compared with early-maturing IR60. Survival was studied at early tillering, maximum tillering, panicle initiation, booting, and flowering.

Three seedlings were transplanted per clay pot on a staggered schedule so

plants of the five ages could be simultaneously infested with insects. Each pot was a replication and treatments were replicated 10 times. Before larval infestation, tillers were thinned to 12/pot and 10 first-instar larvae were placed one on each. Two tillers were uninfested. Plants were placed in a 20- × 100-cm mylar film cage. YSB adults were collected and counted when they emerged. Percentage survival was determined:

$$\frac{\text{No. of adults}}{\text{No. of larvae used to infest the plant}} \times 100$$

Survival on IR46 was lowest at early tillering and panicle initiation, and highest at booting (see table). Survival

Survival of 1st-instar YSB larva to the adult stage on medium-duration IR46 and early-maturing IR60 at different plant growth stages, IRRI.

Variety	Growth duration (d)	Survival ^a (%)				
		Early tillering	Maximum tillering	Panicle initiation	Booting	Flowering
IR46	130	44 c	66 b	35 c	85 a	60 b
IR60	110	73 a	43 c	55 b	73 a	70 a

^a In a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

was intermediate at maximum tillering and flowering. Survival on IR60 was lowest at maximum tillering and panicle initiation and equally high at early tillering, booting, and flowering. Results indicate that the high level of resistance

at IR46 panicle initiation is at least partially due to low larval survival. The reason for the different responses of the two varieties to YSB was not determined. □

Effect of slow-release N fertilizers on stem borer (SB) and sheath rot (ShR) incidence and on rice grain yield

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We studied the effect of slow release N fertilizers on SB and ShR incidence and grain yield of IR20 in 1983-84.

SB and ShR incidence was significantly lower with neem cake-coated urea at both

Effect of slow-release N fertilizers on SB and ShR incidence and rice grain yield,^a Tirunelveli, India.

N source	75 kg N/ha			100 kg N/ha		
	SB (% white heads)	ShR-infected tillers (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	SB (% white-heads)	ShR-infected tillers (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Prilled urea	23 c	41 b	1.2 a	21 b	50 c	1.2 a
Neem cake-coated urea at 20%	6 a	31 a	1.5 a	5 a	33 a	1.5 a
Coaltar-coated urea at 1%	14 b	38 b	1.4 a	17 b	40 b	1.5 a
Urea supergranules	16 b	40 b	1.3 a	17 b	42 b	1.3 a

^a In a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

N levels (see table). Differences in grain yield were not statistically significant.

Heavy rain (500 mm during flowering and maturity stages) reduced grain yield. □

Preventing tungro (RTV) by applying insecticides to control green leafhopper (GLH) in Bangladesh

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We tested two insecticide treatments for control of GLH *Nephotettix virescens* and RTV. Carbofuran 3G at 3 kg ai/ha was incorporated in the seedbed before planting seeds, or diazinon 60 EC at 0.6 litre ai/ha was sprayed on seedlings 10 and 20 d after sowing.

In the seedbed, 21-d-old seedlings were inoculated with RTV viruliferous GLH for 4 d. The seedlings were transplanted in 14 treatment plots, each with

RTV infection on TN1 plants treated with carbofuran and diazinon at different growth stages, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.^a

Seedbed treatment	Treatment in transplanted plot			Hills ^b (no.) showing RTV symptoms	
	Land preparation	Max tillering	Panicle initiation	%	Severity ^c
None ^d	-	-	-	30.3 bc	4.3 abc
None	-	-	-	50.8 d	6.3 c
C	-	-	-	27.8 bc	4.3 abc
C	C	-	-	14.0 a	3.0 a
C	C	C	-	15.0 a	3.7 ab
C	C	C	C	8.7 a	3.0 a
None ^d	C	C	C	10.0 a	3.7 ab
None	C	C	C	19.9 abc	3.0 a
D-60	-	-	-	58.6 d	5.7 bc
D-60	D-10	-	-	53.9 bc	5.7 bc
D-60	D-10	D-10	-	31.3 bc	3.7 bc
D-60	D-10	D-10	D-10	53.2 bc	4.3 abc
None ^d	D-10	D-10	D-10	12.0 ab	3.7 ab
None	D-10	D-10	D-10	26.6 abc	3.7 ab

^a A dash (-) means no insecticide was applied. C = carbofuran, D-60 = diazinon 60 EC, D-10 = diazinon 10G. ^b Means of 3 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. ^c Rated by the 1976 Standard evaluation system for rice. ^d Not inoculated with RTV.